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THE TRAJECTORIES OF TOURISM VENTURES VIS-À-VIS
PROSPECTS OF POVERTY ALLEVIATION IN SOUTH ASIA –
AN EXPLORATORY REPORTAGE

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ABSTRACT

Poverty is a ubiquitous and prevalent predicament in South Asia which is home to a quarter of the world population and nearly one third of the poor people in the world. Albeit, there has been a sizeable reduction in the poverty headcount ratio since 1990, about 256 million people remain in absolute poverty in the region. However, the region; is blessed with enthralling natural resources and cultural embodiments. These assets are promoted as tourism products which in turn would fetch foreign as well as domestic earnings. Tourism industry is experiencing sustained and substantial growth, contributing a total of 9.8% to the world GDP and 9.5% to the global employment. In spite of possessing incredible facets of tourism, South Asian nations haven't been able to woo its fair share of tourists. The primary aim of this paper is to highlight the potential of tourism as a panacea for poverty issues in the South Asian context. Further, tourism-poverty studies have been mostly focused on African or South East Asian regions. This paper is an attempt to bridge the exiting gap by assimilating the leads from various dossiers, consultancy reports, and case studies that underpins the potential of tourism in mitigating poverty in South Asia. The present work provides a broad picture of poverty issues in South Asia and also presents an in-depth review of the tourism- poverty linkages. The lacunae in terms of infrastructure, planning and promotion in the realm of tourism in South Asia are dealt in this paper.

Key Words :

Destinations, Poverty Alleviation, Pro-poor Tourism. South Asian development

"As long as poverty, injustice and gross inequality persist in our world, none of us can truly rest." - Nelson Mandela

PROLOGUE

If Mandela's righteous words are to be followed then this is definitely not the time that we should rest. The sad truth is even after the efforts of various multinational, national and regional organisations; poverty still runs rampant in various forms and types across the world. It (poverty) is a multi-dimensional and complex stumbling block in the path of development and humanity in general. Its effects are pervasive and all encompassing (UI Haq 2000). By the end of 2013, 767 million people lived under the claws of absolute poverty (World Bank 2016). The main causative factor for the increasing poverty is the escalating population and the corresponding depreciation of resources.

The region of South Asia exhibits a paradoxical story. It is a region that is often characterised by startling disparities and acute contrasts: a land which is growing at a rapid pace towards economic liberation while the absolute number of poor in the region is also on the rise (Devarajan 2007). It is home to the second highest number of poor in the whole world. Out of the 767 million poor people, 389 million live in Sub-Saharan Africa and 256 million reside in South Asia which in total accounts for 71% of the world's poor (World Bank 2016). Further, the fact that it is the most populated region in the world, adds misery to the whole situation. Therefore, in order to achieve and sustain development at the world level, it is imperative that the poverty agenda of South Asia must be addressed cautiously.

In this context, it can be noted that the poverty alleviation process of South Asia is mostly driven by primary sectors i.e. agriculture and allied activities (Harriss 1992, World Bank 2007). However, with the passage of time it has been observed that the primary sector hasn't been able to alleviate poverty up to the level expected (Aziz 1979, Schutjer & Stokes 1984). Therefore, there has been emergence of different forms of alternative or complimentary mechanism for livelihood sustenance and poverty reduction. Tourism is one such sector that has gathered much attention in the new millennium, thanks to its power to alleviate poverty and generate a major portion of the earnings. The power of tourism as a poverty alleviating mechanism has been echoed and advocated by many authors across the academia.

Globally, the tourism sector is touching the horizons of growth and showing a sustained pattern of development. The South Asian region is full of both natural and manmade attractions that have immense potential to be world class tourism destinations. These destinations can act as a platform where various endeavours pertaining to livelihood generation can be generated and consequently poverty can be alleviated. In this connection, many multilateral and bilateral institutions like the UN, World Bank, Overseas Development Institute (ODI), Department for International Development (DFID), Asian Development Bank etc. carried out many developmental measures to alleviate poverty through Tourism. In addition, the nations of South Asian region bring out policy reforms to sensitise about poverty issues by drawing the power from tourism induced development.

The present paper initiates by providing a brief account of poverty position in South Asia. It highlights the potential of tourism as a panacea for poverty issues in the South Asian context. Further, tourism-poverty studies have been mostly focused on African or South East Asian regions. This paper strives to unveil the exiting gap by assimilating the leads from various dossiers, consultancy reports, and case studies that underpins the potential of tourism in mitigating poverty in South Asia. How the dynamics of tourism development tend to interpret societal welfare measures and efforts is deliberately focused in this work.

STUDY OBJECTIVES

This work revolves around three key objectives. The first objective is to provide the current profile of poverty in South Asia. Even though poverty of South Asia is itself a broad area, efforts have been made to provide an overall picture to set the tone of the paper. Across the tourism academia, there is a strong voice rising to make tourism work for the poor. Therefore, the next objective is to build arguments in favour of tourism as a potent tool for poverty alleviation. The final objective is to report the policies formulated by the South Asian nations to integrate tourism industry operatives and engagements with efforts to eliminate poverty.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The paper adopts desk based review process which includes reviews of both online and offline resources. Various articles in reputed journals were first identified through EBSCO, Science Direct, Google Scholar and JSTOR online resources. Tourism development, poverty eradication and South Asian perspectives were the keywords that were used to extract the lead works. Following this, various policy papers, reports of various government, private and NGO organisations were accessed. To draw concrete inferences, a number of media communications, newspaper columns, and magazine pieces pertaining to these variables were collected and data was reported in a logical manner. In addition attempt was made to establish a link between the data collected and South Asian destinations' betterment of living standards. Finally, the draft of the paper was prepared and reviewed twice to eliminate the out dated and irrelevant deductions.

POVERTY IN SOUTH ASIA- REPORTAGE

The region of South Asia marks a special place in the world geography given the fact that it is the most populated (approx. 25% of the world's population) and most densely populated (289 people/km²) geographical region in the whole world (World Population Meters 2017). According to World Bank (2016) report titled "South Asia economic focus", the region is the fastest growing region in the whole world and has defied the sluggish economic growth of the world. India, the biggest nation in the region is showing great signs of progression in terms of 5-7% growth in GDP, increased per capita income and better living conditions (Ding & Masha 2012).

However, even after this hastened process of growth the contribution of South Asia to World GDP is abysmally low (3.62%) relative to the percentage of the population (24.8%) residing in it (World Bank 2016). It is also home to the 33% of the world's poor that accounts for 15% of the total population of the South Asian region (Roser & Ortiz 2017). South Asia is the second highest geographical region in terms of poverty head count ratio preceding

Sub-Saharan Africa which is home to half of the absolute poor in the whole world. But taking into account the population indicator, Sub-Saharan Africa is way behind South Asia.

Unemployment is a major indicator of poverty. Maldives tops the list of the most unemployed countries in South Asia with around 11.2% of the people still unemployed. Afghanistan and Pakistan are the next two countries in the list. Even though only 3.6% of the Indian population is unemployed, there is severe scarcity of skilled labour in the Indian markets. Under nourishment due to food scarcity shows the extent of poverty in the country. Sri Lanka, India, and Pakistan share are infamous as the most under nourished countries in the Southern Asian region.

Inequality (Deininger & Squire 1996) in the region of South Asia is the most prominent reason behind poverty. Almost in all the countries in South Asia the top 20% of the people acquire more than 40% of the wealth in the country and the bottom 20% is held up with less than 9% of the wealth. This implies that the gap in wealth accumulation is about 35-40% across all South Asian countries. Also, there is a great confusion in defining the term poor which makes it even harder for the policy makers to design pro-poor policies (Irfan 2000). The rigid caste based society stands as a major obstacle in the paths of growth in South Asia (Mehta & Shah 2003). Adding oil to the fire are the problems of corruption, gender inequality and lack of education.

TOURISM LED POVERTY ALLEVIATION

Tourism industry across the globe is celebrated as a "sunrise industry", thanks to its labour intensive nature (Hall 2005) and for taking the lead in harnessing economic growth and reducing poverty especially in the developing countries (Winters, Corral & Mora 2013). Muganda, Sahli & Smith (2010) argue that tourism is one of the highly rated components of development strategy in Least Developed Countries (LDCs) and in nations that aspire to achieve economic growth and alleviation of poverty. Tourism is often used as a catalyst for galvanising the processes for growth in economic condition, modernisation and prosperity more specifically in poorer countries

(Williams 1998). Jafari (2001) in his works echoed William's statement in the portion of advocacy approach of tourism.

Tourism led poverty alleviation may be categorised under three broad categories as described by Mitchell & Ashley (2010). They are (i) direct, (ii) secondary and (iii) dynamic effects. The *direct effect* comprises of income earned by non-labour people by selling the goods and services. The *secondary effect* is further classified in to two categories i.e. indirect effects which means purchase of raw materials and other inputs from other tourism supporting firms and induced effects that puts limelight on income spent by the non-labour class of people like tourism firm owners and employees (of the direct category). The dynamic effect takes into account the overall development of the locality by the investments induced by tourism sector in the fields like infrastructure, human capital, and environment. Slee, Farr, and Snowdon (1997) put limelight on the fact that each unit of capital spent on tourism industry generates more number of jobs than any other industry. Tourism industry also facilitates income multiplier effects (Archer & Fletcher 1996). Due to 'Multiplier Effects' the income generated on the top trickles down to the poorer segments of people through different channels.

Another perennial cause of poverty is inequality. Tourism has been regarded as a solution for the problems of inequality, conflicts and is regarded as the gateway to world peace (IIPT 2004). That apart, tourism industry supports the basic idea of gender equality by inclusion of women in the decision making and tourism development process (Ashley & Roe 2002:61). The apex body of world tourism, UNWTO has embarked on the theme of poverty alleviation time and again. In the year 2005, UNWTO declared the tourism sector as a 'War on poverty' that fosters upward movement of the poorer sections of the societies and endorsed the first goal of MDGs. In his works Dann (2002) highlighted the importance of tourism industry by quoting it as 'Passport to Development'.

Being a labour intensive sector, tourism often creates new job opportunities, many of those are part time in nature, require fewer skills and little investment and suited to the women, youth and disadvantaged groups. After realising that tourism can be utilised as

a socially responsible poverty alleviation tool, The UNWTO, that promotes equitable, sustainable and universally accessible tourism, has fixed '10 Principles for Pursuing Poverty Alleviation through Tourism' to make tourism more accessible to the poor.

1. *All aspects and types of tourism can and should be concerned about poverty alleviation.*
2. *All governments should include poverty alleviation as a key aim of tourism development and consider tourism as a possible tool for reducing poverty.*
3. *The competitiveness and economic success of tourism businesses and destinations is critical to poverty alleviation - without this the poor cannot benefit.*
4. *All tourism businesses should be concerned about the impact of their activities on local communities and seek to benefit the poor through their actions.*
5. *Tourism destinations should be managed with poverty alleviation as a central aim that is built into strategies and action plans.*
6. *A sound understanding of how tourism functions in destinations is required, including how tourism income is distributed and who benefits from this.*
7. *Planning and development of tourism in destinations should involve a wide range of interests, including participation and representation from poor communities.*
8. *All potential impacts of tourism on the livelihood of local communities should be considered, including current and future local and global impacts on natural and cultural resources.*
9. *Attention must be paid to the viability of all projects involving the poor, ensuring access to markets and maximizing opportunities for beneficial links with established enterprises.*
10. *Impacts of tourism on poverty alleviation should be effectively monitored.*

[Source: Manual on Tourism and Poverty Alleviation, Practical Steps for Destinations. UNWTO & SNV 2010]

In developing countries, it is very common to see that most of the tourism benefits go to the upper level of the society that restricts the poor and downtrodden to have significant gain from this ever-growing and vibrant industry and it increases the gap between the poor and the rich in the society. In this regard, many of the South Asian countries have framed their policies and adopted different tourism strategies to make tourism more pro-poor so that it can achieve the ultimate goal i.e. reduce poverty. Lemma (2014), divulged that tourism brings greater benefit to the economy of smaller nations although the relative importance is greater for particular countries.

TOURISM IN SOUTH ASIA

The geography of South Asia shows a great range of diversity and uniqueness. The highest two mountain peaks (Everest and K2) is present in South Asia. It is the birth place of four different religions and people of all the religions reside in this region. The region features some of the best river systems and plains (like Gangetic plains) in the world. Thousands of languages are spoken in this region (De Alwis 2010). The biodiversity seen in South Asia is second to none. Starting from the mangrove forests of Sundarbans to the pristine beaches of Maldives, South Asia provides an experience like no other. South Asia is known not only for natural attractions, but also for man-made attractions too. The biggest Hindu temple of Brihadeswara, the majestic church of Bom Basilica, the Lotus temple of Bahai faith and the daragah of Nizzamudin; all religious establishments have found a place in South Asia. It is also home to heritage marvels such as the Taj Mahal, Ajanta, Sigiriya, Thimpu, and Taxila, the heritage and cultures of the region date back thousands of years (Smith 2000, Smith et al. 2001).

Travel and Tourism plays a great role in South Asia in shaping the economy. In terms of the direct and total contribution to GDP of South Asia, Travel and Tourism (T&T) contributes 3.2% (US\$91bn) and 8.9% (US\$252.9bn) respectively. Similarly in terms of the direct and total contribution to the employment in South Asia, the

contribution of T&T is around 5.0% (28,658,000 jobs) and 8.3% (47,998,000 jobs) respectively. Considering the growth scenario, South Asian region is forecasted to have the highest growth potential for the upcoming years (WTTC 2017a). Tourism in South Asia is riding the waves of growth by achieving 12% of the total world tourist arrivals by 2014. There was a steep growth of 7.4% in the tourist arrivals between the years 2013 and 2014. Further, T&T is one of the sectors that attract huge amount of capital in to the South Asian economy. In the year 2016, 5.4% (US\$39.9bn) of total investment in South Asia was under the T&T sector.

In India, T&T is a source for 9.6% (total contribution) of the GDP and provides 9.3% of the total job employment (WTTC 2017b). For island countries like Maldives and Sri Lanka tourism opens the doors for FDI that results in commendable economic development. Nepal and Myanmar are countries of verdant mountains, yet the basic sources to earn livelihood and food are difficult, due to the hostile terrains. In those cases tourism is turning out to be a boon that is stimulating not only economic but social and environmental development as well. Though, Pakistan and Afghanistan are blessed with flora and fauna they are yet to realise the fruits of tourism owing to political instability and terrorism.

THE FACETS OF TOURISM VIS-À-VIS POVERTY ALLEVIATION IN SOUTH ASIA

As stated earlier, poverty and tourism are having its presence in the South Asian scenario. What poverty is still posing a threat to the South Asian economy, tourism is emerging to be one of the most pragmatic sector solutions. But, it is much difficult to measure the impact of tourism on poverty in economic terms because the organisations that publish the tourism statistics (namely WTO or WTTC) do not provide any reference to the poverty statistics and vice versa. Therefore, it will be wise to look into the strategies and policies adopted by each country with respect to the tourism led poverty alleviation (Lemma 2014). The section below provides a look into the various ways that the South Asian nations have adopted to achieve poverty reduction through tourism.

COUNTRY SPECIFIC COINAGE OF TOURISM POLICIES AND STRATEGIES FOR POVERTY ALLEVIATION

INDIA

From the Indian perspective, *The National Tourism Policy, 2002* connects tourism with rural development, employment potential, and business linkages but was insufficient in its approach to make tourism more pro-poor. In 2006, Kerala government decided to implement Responsible Tourism to make the State's tourism policies more poor-friendly. The initiative kicked off in 2007 with local hotels agreeing to purchase food from local producers and to permit the local artisans to sell their souvenirs to the tourists staying at hotels. It resulted in the spurt of a good working relation between the hoteliers and the local farmers and artisans. The programme has been particularly successful after including women in its activities, resulting in the inclusion of 760 women in multiple tourism enterprises. The Government of India thus sees the programme as a successful system that can be replicated at the national level (GoI 2013). The Ministry of Tourism (2010-2011 Annual Report), again turned the spotlight on the pro-poor tourism approach and considered tourism as an effective tool for poverty alleviation. The aim of the 'Strategic Action Plan' (that was in vogue until 2015) was to provide the people a better quality of life through overall development and tourism promotion (GoI 2011). It gave special importance to implementing more effective tourism strategies and increase the number of tourists, to develop human resources, to facilitate the tourists with highly efficient tourism infrastructure and to promote cultural and eco-tourism. Moreover, India's '12th Five Year Plan 2012 – 2017' acknowledges the pro-poor role of tourism and therefore, suggests the Government institutions to ensure greater participation of the poor people in the tourism sector.

Apart from that, a few more points linked with poverty eradication, have been also discussed such as joint partnership ventures between formal and informal enterprises, reframing of helpful policy and planning framework, and increased participation of host communities in the tourism planning and decision making

process. It also mentions the need for women empowerment in the sector (GoI 2013). Recent studies also reveal that in India, the multiplier and poverty alleviation effects of domestic tourists are more significant than that of foreign tourists (Rasul & Manandhar 2009). Despite the fact that foreign tourists are much ahead of the domestic tourists in terms of daily expenditure, they are coming in small groups while the domestic tourists, travelling in a larger number and also spending more time (days) at a specific destination in comparison with the foreign tourists are now dominating the Indian tourism market. As a result, in India, now there is a growing recognition of domestic tourism that is no doubt helping the host community economically.

SRI LANKA

Sri Lanka tourism is based on its potential contribution to climate change mitigation, aiming to be a carbon neutral destination by 2018 (Lemma 2014; De Alwis 2010). Tourism sector is always seen in this country as one of the key drivers for economic growth. The key objectives of the Sri Lankan 'Tourism Development Strategy' (2011–2016) revolve around the following points: (a) FDI (Foreign Direct Investment) in the tourism sector, (b) creation of new jobs, (c) overall infrastructure development and (d) conservation of nature to minimize the negative impacts of tourism on environment the core strategy to draw tourists' attention towards this island country though the role of tourism in poverty alleviation has not been stated clearly. Yet, reports from the stakeholders and also the visitors' comment elucidate that the tour operations have become incredibly responsible of late with lot of capacity building programmes and endeavours of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) reinforcing the ideals of responsible tourism.

BHUTAN

Though Bhutan's tourism policy does not clearly mention how tourism can be utilised as a tool for poverty reduction, it is based on 'high value, low impact' tourism, the approach that has been already adopted by countries like Tanzania where tourism sector

has achieved significant success and the poor people living near the tourism zones have gained from tourism (Mitchell, Keane & Laidlaw 2009). Moreover, Bhutan's tourism industry also emphasises on its environment, cultural heritages, socio-economic development and overall sustainable tourism operations, often bundled together with pro-poor operations, aimed at setting up both pro-poor and sustainable tourism practices (Saville 2002; Tresilian 2006, Dhakal et al. 2007). SNV, a Netherland based not-for-profit international development organisation, working on agriculture, energy, and water, sanitation & hygiene along with Bhutanese Tourism Association and the Tourism Council of Bhutan started capacity building training programmes since 2005 and also successfully implemented 'Responsible Business in Tourism Programme' that increases the recognition of the value of pro-poor tourism products and enforces the Bhutanese companies to take positive steps in extending tourism opportunities to the host community, especially to the poor.

PAKISTAN

Pakistan formulated its Tourism Master Plan in 2000. The 'Medium Term Development Framework', an outline of Pakistan's tourism sector within the time period from 2005 to 2010 discusses the role of tourism in enhancing the value or status of country's cultural heritage but it fails to make any significant reference towards poverty alleviation. In addition, neither Pakistan's Annual Plan for 2013–2014 nor its Vision 2025 Plan has made any notable reference to tourism. A time series analysis of the tourism trend in Pakistan clearly points out that the unique social practices, rites, and customs are not interpreted with tourism promotion which appears to be lacunae in the tourism policy framework. Tourism is absolutely a panacea to resolve many adversity faced by a country rich in resplendent culture and heritage.

MALDIVES

Maldives, world's one of the most successful island destinations, has adopted a tourism business model that advocates for building

strong partnerships with the overseas investors, tour operators and some of the best international and regional brand names. The primary objective of the country's ongoing tourism strategy, based on a five year (2013-2017) rolling Tourism Master Plan, is to become a carbon neutral destination by taking special care of its pristine environments. Paradoxically, although the Maldivian Government has found its tourism sector possessing the potentiality to be pro-poor, any clear strategy regarding that is still missing in its policies, particularly from the Tourism Master Plan. It seems that the Government has not linked tourism with Maldivian society and therefore, lightly touches upon the pro-poor movement in its way forward (Lemma 2014). The National Development Plan (2006–2010) also failed to show any clear linkage between tourism and poverty reduction, although tourism is considered as a source of economic growth and employment (IMF 2008).

NEPAL

Since the Nepal Government's Ninth five year plan (1997-2002), poverty alleviation has remained the major objective in Nepal. The tenth five year Plan (2002-2007), named Poverty Alleviation Strategy Paper focused mainly on poverty (Bista 2006) and the aim was to achieve a sustainable reduction in poverty levels from 38% to 30% at the end of 2007 (NTS 2002). According to Dahal et al. (1999), tourism has the ability to bring more benefits to the Nepalese economy compared to agriculture which is found to be a lagging sector. From 2001 to 2007, the pro-poor tourism development model was tested for the Rural Poverty Alleviation Project (MoCTCA 2007). The Tourism Strategy 2008 initially allowed tourism to create alternative sources of income that helped the country's economy to grow and on the other side it reduced the poverty to some extent. But by 2012, it was realised that due to low investment from the government side and lack of assistance from the private stakeholders, Nepal's tourism sector's growth rates failed to meet its expectations (GoN 2012). Therefore, Nepal Government promptly included tourism within its Immediate Action Plan on Economic Development & Prosperity (GoN 2012) to

increase employment opportunities especially in its rural areas, largely affected by the blight of poverty. The IAP emphasised on (a) investments for the improvement in transport infrastructure, (b) eco-tourism, and (c) cultural/religious tourism. Moreover, the Three Year approach Paper 2010/11–2012/13 (National Development Strategy) acknowledged tourism as a catalyst of overall growth and clearly mentioned its role in reducing poverty (GoN 2010). Tourism Policy, 2009; NTY, 2011 (Nepal Tourism Year); Tourism Policy, 2025 and Tourism Vision 2020—all underscores the fact that Nepal Government has idealised tourism as an effective vehicle for regional development and is trying to mitigate its associate threats such as economic crisis and climate change (Adler et al. 2013) and priorities have been accorded to developing tourism infrastructure, increasing activities, creating employment in rural areas and finally equitable distribution of tourism benefits at the grassroots level (Bhandari 2012).

BANGLADESH

The Strategic Master Plan for Tourism Development, 1990; the 'National Tourism Policy', 1992; and the 'National Tourism Policy', 2009—all consider a common fact that Bangladesh's Tourism sector can be an essential tool to alleviate poverty, but at the same time, none of these policies or Tourism Development Plans have clearly stated specifically what type of pro-poor measures could / should be implemented to accomplish the goal.

COORDINATED EFFORTS BY SOUTH ASIAN COUNTRIES IN TOURISM PROMOTION AND POVERTY ALLEVIATION

In early 1980s, the WTO (World Tourism Organisation i.e. now UNWTO) set up a Secretariat in Colombo, the capital state of Sri Lanka, to promote this region as a tourism hub though this noble initiative was nipped in the bud because of lack of support and interest. Later in the 1990s, the SAARC leaders realised that tourism can bring socio-economic and cultural prosperity in any region

and therefore SAARC Chambers of Commerce and Industry (SCCI) mentioned the need for better and more effective steps if development is to succeed in the world's poorest countries. In 1997, countries like Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, and Nepal formed the *South Asian Growth Quadrangle* and it was supported by *The Asian Development Bank* (ADB). In later stage India, Nepal, Bhutan, Bangladesh along with Sri Lanka formed the *South Asia Sub-regional Economic Cooperation* (SASEC) to reduce rural poverty by taking the advantages of complementarities and synergies among the member countries. In 1999, the *UN Commission on Sustainable Development* urged the governments to develop suitable strategies in co-operation with all major groups, indigenous and local communities to maximise the potential of tourism for eradicating poverty. In 2004, these countries came up with a tourism development plan within the 'SASEC Framework' with twenty three projects and seven sub-regional programmes aiming at significant growth of tourism leading towards sustainable economic growth, reduction of rural poverty through sub-regional coordinated efforts, joint marketing initiatives, repositioning of regional tourism spots as tourist friendly destinations, agreements upon product themes, private sector development and overall improvement of tourism links within the member countries. A promotional tagline *Magic That Is South Asia* was coined and many activities were proposed to celebrate the year, 2005 (the 20th year of establishment of SAARC) as *South Asia Tourism Year*.

Because of the rigorous promotional efforts by the nations in this region in the realm of tourism for several decades, most of the South Asian countries are now performing up to the mark from the view point of regional dynamism, whereas India and Maldives are exceptionally good in showing their prowess. Though as per *UNESCAP 2008 Report*, Europe and Asian region (including East, South East or the Asia Pacific regions) are still far ahead in terms of receiving visitors and gaining benefits from tourism. Alwis (2010), mentioned one of the three main problems that prevent South Asian Tourism to take off is the failure to distribute the growth achieved to reduce poverty. Therefore, to tap the maximum economic benefit from tourism and to promote intra-regional

tourism for ensuring overall regional prosperity, there is always a need for coordinated efforts among the countries to improve the tourism infrastructure (Jamieson, Goodwin & Edmunds 2004, Rasul and Manandhar 2009, Harun 2010). In this connection, Fritz and Menocal (2007), feels that "better and more effective steps are needed if development is to succeed in the world's poorest countries". According to Scheyvens (2007), "Without genuine government intervention the poorest are bound to carry a heavier burden in terms of costs of environmental degradation, cultural commodification and social displacement".

INFERENCES AND DISCUSSIONS

The region of South Asia is blessed with fabulous tourism attractions – both natural and cultural. Still, the disparities in terms of levels of tourism development as regards the countries of South Asia are clearly evident. Intra-regional trails, which could have been path breaking is nowhere in the agenda. It is a paradox that SAARC Summits have time and again missed out on this aspect. The poverty stricken countries of South Asia are reeling under the pressure of cross border terrorism. Though there is increased realisation that tourism can go to a great extent to eradicate the distresses caused by poverty. So far, little progression has been made to tap its potential of poverty alleviation in a consistent and continuous manner. Ironically, majority of the countries which have outstanding facets of tourism at the local levels have shown least concern in subscribing to the latest developments in the field such as Voluntourism, pro-poor tourism, technological adoption in hospitality, supplementary accommodation etc.

It is high time that the destination planners express sensitivity to break the shackles and unveil the potential of socially responsible tourism in giving impetus to the poverty elimination programmes. Socially responsible tourism urges tourists to invest, develop, and respect the local cultures and social morals and values. It also prods local communities to offer safety and comfort to the visitors whereby their livelihood sustenance is leveraged.

EPILOGUE

It is almost impossible to show a concrete statistical trend that establishes the link between tourism development and poverty reduction at the world level as the empirical evidences are scarce in the existing literature. The paper attempts to provide the macro level picture of the poverty problem in South Asia and then shifts the attention to the tourism potentials existing in the region. Later, it argues that the problem of poverty can be reduced substantially by linking community development schemes and activities of host population with the tourism sector. The whole narrative of this work is based on the strong background of literature that advocates tourism as a panacea for poverty alleviation. In the final section, the various policies, regulations and strategies taken at the national level by various South Asian countries for making tourism pro-poor are cited.

REFERENCES

- Adler C. E., McEvoy D., Chhetri P. & Kruk E. (2013) The role of tourism in a changing climate for conservation and development. A problem-oriented study in the Kailash Sacred Landscape, *Nepal. Policy Sciences*, 46(2), 161-178.
- Archer B. & Fletcher J. (1996) The economic impact of tourism in the Seychelles. *Annals of tourism research*, 23(1), 32-47.
- Ashley C. & Roe D. (2002) Making tourism work for the poor: strategies and challenges in southern Africa. *Development Southern Africa*, 19(1), 61-82.
- Ashley C. & Mitchell J. (2010) *Tourism and Poverty Reduction: Pathways to Prosperity*, Earthscan.
- Asian Development Bank. (2016) SOUTH ASIA SUBREGIONAL ECONOMIC COOPERATION OPERATIONAL PLAN 2016- 2025. Mandaluyong City, Philippines:Asian Development Bank. Retrieved from <https://www.adb.org/documents/sasec-operational-plan-2016-2025>.
- Aziz S. (1979) Rural Development-Learning from China. *VRÜ Verfassung und Recht in Übersee*, 12(4), 425-427.
- Bhandari K. R. (2012) *Tourism Policies and Priorities*.
- Bista R. (2006) A Tourism Plan to Alleviate Rural Poverty in Nepal. *e-Review of Tourism Research*, 4(3), 50-55.
- Dahal M. K., Acharya K. P., Dahal D. R., Bhattachan K. B. & Nepal. M. K. (1999) *Development Challenges for Nepal*. Nepal Foundation for Advanced Studies.

- Dani M. S. Graham (2002) 'Tourism and development'. Edited by Vandana Desai & Robert B. Potter. The companion to development studies. London: Arnold.
- De Alwis K. (2010) Promoting Tourism in South Asia. Promoting Economic Cooperation in South Asia: Beyond SAFTA, 259-276.
- Deininger K. & Squire L. (1996) A new data set measuring income inequality. *The World Bank Economic Review*, 10(3), 565-591.
- Devarajan S. (2007) Can South Asia End Poverty in a Generation?. UN Chronicle, (XLIV). Retrieved from <https://un Chronicle.un.org/article/can-south-asia-end-poverty-generation-more-inclusive-growth-and-faster-human-development-are>
- Dhakal D. P., Khadka M., Sharma S. & Choevgyal L. (2007) Lessons Learned: Nepal's Experience Implementing Sustainable Rural Tourism Development Model of Tourism for Rural Poverty Alleviation Programme. Kathmandu, Nepal: Tourism for Rural Poverty Alleviation Programme (TRPAP). Field observation, community consultations, consultation with the tourism entrepreneurs.
- Ding D. & Masha A. (2012) India's growth spillovers to South Asia. International Monetary Fund (IMF). IMF Working Paper, WP/12/56, Washington, DC.
- Fritz V. & Menocal A. R. (2007) Developmental states in the new millennium: Concepts and challenges for a new aid agenda. *Development Policy Review*, 25(5), 531-552.
- GoI (2011) "Strategic Action Plan" Government of India, Ministry of Tourism.
- GoI (2013) "Twelfth Five Year Plan (2012-2017): Volume II - Economic Sectors" Government of India, Planning Commission, 2013.
- GoN (2010) "Three Year Plan Approach Paper 2010/11-2012/13" Government of Nepal, National Planning Commission, 2010.
- GoN (2012) "Immediate Action Plan on Economic Development & Prosperity" Government of Nepal, Ministry of Finance, 2012.
- Hall C. M. (2005) Rural wine and food tourism cluster and network development. Rural tourism and sustainable business, 149-164.
- Harriss J. (1992) Rural development: theories of peasant economy and agrarian change. Routledge.
- Harun Y. A. (2010) Regional cooperation in South Asia: Bangladesh perspective. Promoting Regional Cooperation in South Asia: Beyond SAFTA, World Bank, Washington, DC, 279-299.
- IMF (2008) Maldives: Poverty Reduction Strategy Paper International Monetary Fund, January 2008.
- International Institute for Peace Through Tourism (IIPT) (2004) January Newsletter. Retrieved from <http://www.iipt.org/newsletter/January2004.html>.

The Trajectories of Tourism Ventures vis-à-vis Prospects of Poverty Alleviation in South Asia - An Exploratory Reportage

- Irfan M. (2000) Poverty in South Asia. *The Pakistan Development Review*, 114(1-151). Jafari J. (2001)
- Jafari J. (2001) Scientification of Tourism. In V. Smith & M. Hosni. Host and Guest revisited: Tourism issues of 21st Century. Elsevier, 28-41.
- Jamieson W., Goodwin H. & Edmunds C. (2004) Contribution of tourism poverty alleviation pro-poor tourism and the challenge of measuring it. Lemma A. F. (2014) Tourism for Poverty Reduction in South Asia.
- Mehta A. K. & Shah A. (2003) Chronic poverty in India: Incidence and policies. *World Development*, 31(3), 491-511.
- Mitchell J., Keane J. & Laidlaw J. (2009) Making success work for all: Package tourism in Northern Tanzania. Overseas Development Institute.
- MoCTCA (2007) Nepal's experience implementing sustainable development models: Lessons learned. Kathmandu: Government of Nepal Ministry of Culture, Tourism and Civil Aviation and TRPAP.
- Muganda M., Salili M. & A Smith K. (2010) Tourism's contribution to poverty alleviation: A community perspective from Tanzania. *Development Southern Africa*, 27(5), 629-646.
- Rasul G. & Manandhar P. (2009) Prospects and problems in rural tourism in South Asia: A regional perspective. *South Asia Economic Journal*, 10(1), 187-207.
- Roser M. & Ortiz E. (2017) "Global Extreme Poverty". Our World in Data. Retrieved from <https://ourworldindata.org/extreme-poverty/>
- Saville N. M. (2002) Sustainable Ecotourism and eco-enterprise opportunities in the Gulf of Mannar, Tamil Nadu, India. Report of a study conducted by Scheyvens R. (2007) Exploring the tourism-poverty nexus. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 10(2-3), 231-254.
- Schutjer W. A. & Stokes C. S. (1984) Rural development and human ecology. London, Macmillan Publishing Company.
- Slee B., Farr H. & Snowdon P. (1997) The economic impact of tourism: Types of rural tourism. *Journal of agricultural economics*, 48(12), 179-189.
- Smith R. A. (2000) Tourism planning and development in South and South East Asia. *Tourism in South and Southeast Asia: Issues and context*, 2000.
- Smith V. L. & Brent M. (2001) Hosts and guests revisited: tourism in the 21st century-introduction. Hosts and guests revisited: tourism issues of the 21st century, 1-11.
- Tresilian D. (2006) Poverty Alleviation and Community-based Tourism Experiences from Central and South Asia. UNESCO.
- Ullah M. (2000) Human development in South Asia 1999: The state of governance. USA, Oxford University Press.
- Williams S. (1998) Tourism geography. London, Routledge.

Priyankrutina Mohanty, Aradh Gantait, Dr. Anu Chandra

- Winters P., Corral L. & Mora A. M. (2013) Assessing the role of tourism poverty alleviation: A research agenda. *Development Policy Review*, 31(2), 77-202.
- World Bank (2007) World development report 2008: Agriculture for development. World Bank.
- World Bank (2016) South Asia economic focus. Washington DC. Retrieved from <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/bitstream/handle/10986/25096/71464809927.pdf?sequence=2&isAllowed=y>
- World Bank (2016) GDP (current US\$) | Data. Data.worldbank.org. Retrieved 1 January 2017, from <http://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.MKTR.CD>
- World Population Meter (2017) "World Population Clock: 7.4 Billion People (2017) - Worldometers". Worldometers.info. <http://www.worldometers.info/world-population/>.
- World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC) (2017a) TRAVEL & TOURISM ECONOMIC IMPACT 2017. WTTC. Retrieved from <https://www.wttc.org/-/media/files/reports/economic-impact-research/regions-2017/southasia2017.pdf>
- World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC) (2017b) TRAVEL & TOURISM ECONOMIC IMPACT 2017. WTTC. Retrieved from <https://www.wttc.org/-/media/files/reports/economic-impact-research/countries-2017/india2017.pdf>

WEBLIOGRAPHY:

- <http://blogs.worldbank.org/psd/should-we-be-promoting-tourism-sector-investment>
- http://boi.gov.bd/index.php/component/businesslaws/?view=lawdetails&law_id=1136
- <http://condesan.org/mtnforum/sites/default/files/publication/files/1611.pdf>
- <http://pc.gov.pk/mtdf26-Tourism/26-Tourism%20Dev.pdf>
- <http://step.unwto.org/content/tourism-and-poverty-alleviation-1>
- <http://welcomenepal.com/promotional/event/nepal-tourism-year-2011/>
- <http://www.adb.org/Documents/Reports/>
- <http://www.adb.org/Documents/Reports/SASEC/TourismDevelopment/default.asp?ps=sasec>
- http://www.bangladeshtourism.gov.bd/overview_country_profile.php
- http://www.gwu.edu/~its/unwto/IPC_TourismSector_ShaunMann.pdf
- http://www.iftc.org/wp-content/connect/e7eba380478ec2d9829d9286d3bf329/Tourism+by+Region_June+2013_Final.pdf?MOD=AJPERES
- http://www.nepaltourism.info/aroundkathmandu/bhaktapur_history.html
- http://www.parjatan.gov.bd/index.php?option=com_tourism&view=page&layout=sub_menu&sub_menu_id=131&Itemid=154

The Trajectories of Tourism Ventures vis-à-vis Prospects of Poverty Alleviation in South Asia - An Exploratory Reportage

- http://www.pc.gov.pk/?page_id=137
- http://www.pc.gov.pk/?page_id=367
- <http://www.saarcchamber.com/>
- <http://www.saarc-sec.org/main.php?n=2.10>
- <http://www.tourism.gov.bt/tourism-policy/tourism-policy>
- http://www.tourismfortomorrow.com/Winners_and_Finalists/2011_Winners_and_Finalists/agri-tourism-development-corporation
- <http://www.visitmaldives.com>
- <http://www.visitnepal.com/acap/un.info.np/Net/NeoDocs/View/3288>
- www.earthlung.travel
- www.srilankatourism.org
- <http://www.tourism.gov.bt/>

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